

A Synthesis of Brazilinic Acid.

BY JNANENDRA NATH RAY, SANTOKH SINGH SILOOJA AND
PREM RAJ WADHA.

The present structure of brazilin is dependent on the constitution of brazilinic acid which has been synthesised by Perkin and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **93**, 515) by condensing *m*-hemipinic anhydride and ethyl methoxyphenoxyacetate in very poor yield. In the present paper it has been found that when ethyl methoxyphenoxypropionate is condensed with veratroyl chloride in presence of aluminium chloride there is extrusion of the ester grouping and the substance (I) along with (III) is produced. In view of this an alternative synthesis of brazilinic acid has been described here.

Perkin and Robinson (*loc. cit.*) found that hemipinic anhydride condensed unsatisfactorily with resorcinol dimethyl ether to give a

non-crystalline (chalky) precipitate of 2-hydroxy-4:4':5'-trimethoxybenzoylbenzoic acid (II). We have now prepared this substance from the ketone (I) by nitration, reduction and the subsequent replacement of NH_2 by CN and finally hydrolysing the nitrile to the acid (II). The substance (I) was prepared by the Friedel and Crafts' reaction on *m*-methoxyphenol with veratroyl chloride, when the substance (III) was also formed in the reaction in almost equal amount. The respective structures were assigned after considering the ferric chloride reactions of the two ketones. The acid (II) was condensed with chloroacetic acid in alkaline solution when brazilinic acid (IV), identical with the acid from the natural product, was obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Hydroxy-4:4':5'-trimethoxybenzophenone.—A solution of ethyl *m*-methoxyphenoxypropionate (4.2 g.), veratroyl chloride (4.1 g.) in nitrobenzene (10 c.c.) was cooled to 0° and was gradually treated with a solution of aluminium chloride (6 g.) in nitrobenzene (40 c. c.) with vigorous shaking. After standing for 12 hours, the mixture was decomposed and the solvent removed in steam. The sticky residue was treated in alcoholic solution with potassium hydroxide (2.5 g. in 30 c.c. alcohol) and the solution diluted with water and filtered. After acidification, the viscous mass obtained was crystallised twice from alcohol, m. p. 141° . (Found: C, 66.6; H, 5.6. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 66.7; H, 5.5 per cent). The substance gives a deep violet colour with ferric chloride solution. In one experiment a small amount of a substance (m. p. 175°) was obtained. It is still under investigation but probably it is the substance (III) described below. The substance (m. p. 141°) is identical with the product obtained as below.

Resorcinol monomethyl ether (5 g.) and veratroyl chloride (8 g.) dissolved in nitrobenzene (20 c.c.) were treated with a solution of aluminium chloride (8 g.) in the same solvent (50 c. c.) at 0° . After 3 hours, the temperature of the bath was raised to $10\text{--}16^\circ$ and left for 18 hours with occasional shaking. The mixture after decomposition with ice was freed from the solvent by steam distillation and the non-volatile portion filtered hot. The insoluble portion crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow needles, m. p. 141° . The substance shows the strong violet ferric chloride reaction, dissolves in sodium hydroxide to an yellow solution and develops reddish yellow colour

with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 66.5; H, 5.6. $C_{10}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 66.7; H, 5.5 per cent). The hot aqueous filtrate of the residue after steam distillation furnished a pale coloured crystalline deposit, m.p. 175° after recrystallisation from alcohol. (Found: C, 66.7; H, 5.3. $C_{16}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 66.7; H, 5.5 per cent). This substance (III) shows a much fainter ferric chloride reaction but otherwise possesses properties similar to the foregoing substance.

2-Hydroxy-4 : 4' : 5'-trimethoxy-2-nitrobenzophenone.—The substance (I) (1 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (15 c.c.) by warming to $60-70^\circ$ and then the solution cooled to $50-53^\circ$. 1.5 C.c. of a mixture of nitric acid (d 1.42, 2 c.c.) and acetic acid (2.5 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (0.5 c.c.) was introduced with stirring, the temperature of the mixture being maintained at $48-52^\circ$. After 16 minutes, the nitro compound separated out and was collected after 2 hours. Crystallised from acetic acid it had m.p. 211° . (Found: N, 4.5. $C_{16}H_{15}O_7N$ requires N, 4.2 per cent). The structure follows from the fact that on oxidation it furnishes nitroveratric acid and energetic nitration gives dinitroveratrol.

2-Hydroxy-4 : 4' : 5'-trimethoxy-2-aminobenzophenone hydrochloride was prepared by reducing 1 g. of the foregoing nitro compound in alcohol (100 c.c.) with stannous chloride (6 g.), tin foil (1 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (4—5 c.c.) on the steam bath for 15 minutes. After the removal of tin the solution was concentrated when the *hydrochloride* crystallised out. Recrystallised from alcoholic hydrochloric acid it had m.p. 240° . (Found: N, 4.2. $C_{16}H_{19}O_5NCl$ requires N, 4.1 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-4 : 4' : 5'-trimethoxy-2-cyanobenzophenone.—A solution of the foregoing amine hydrochloride (1 g.) in hot water (80 c.c.) and hydrochloric acid (d 1.16, 1 c.c.) was cooled to 0° and treated with 2.5 c.c. of 1% sodium nitrite solution. After treatment with potassium cuprocyanide and decomposition, the residue was extracted with alcohol whence the cyano compound (m.p. $152-54^\circ$) was isolated. This was not analysed but directly employed in the subsequent operation.

2-Hydroxy-4 : 4' : 5'-trimethoxybenzoylbenzoic acid (II) —An alcoholic solution of the cyano compound isolated in the above experiment was heated with 10 c.c. of 30% sodium hydroxide solution on the steam-bath for 3-4 hours. After the removal of alcohol, the diluted solution was acidified and the precipitated acid was finally

crystallised from hot 80% acetic acid, m.p. 203°. (Found: C, 61.22; H, 4.68. $C_{17}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 61.44; H, 4.8 per cent).

Brazilinic acid (IV).—(A) 2-Hydroxy-4:4':5'-trimethoxy-2-cyanobenzophenone (0.1364 g.) in water (5 c.c.) and 1% sodium hydroxide solution (1.75 c.c.) was treated with chloroacetic acid (0.047 g.) in water (5 c.c.), neutralised by sodium carbonate and refluxed for 7 hours, on the steam-bath. Finally concentrated hydrochloric acid (6 c.c.) was added and heated for further half an hour. After the removal of alcohol, the solids obtained were dissolved in baryta solution till the resulting mixture was slightly alkaline. The filtrate was treated with exact amount of sulphuric acid, boiled with a little acetic acid and filtered. From the filtrate, a substance, m.p. 208°-209° was isolated which revealed no difference when compared with brazilinic acid obtained from the oxidation of trimethylbrazilin and had mixed m.p. 209°. It also developed the characteristic red colour with sulphuric acid.

(B) 2-Hydroxy-4:4':5'-trimethoxybenzoylbenzoic acid (II) (0.4 g.) in water (10 c.c.) was neutralised with sodium hydroxide solution (7.6 c.c. of 1%). To this a neutralised solution of chloroacetic acid (0.15 g.) in water (5 c.c.) was added and the mixture heated on the steam bath for 7 hours. After acidification the product was crystallised from hot dilute acetic acid, m.p. 208-209° and disclosed no difference when compared with the natural and synthetic brazilinic acid as described above.